

Initial Models and Serialisability in Abstract Dialectical Frameworks

Technical appendix

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3 Characterising Initial Models in ADFs

Proposition 1. *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF and $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is the corresponding ADF. $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ is an admissible set of \mathcal{F} , if and only if v_S is an admissible model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$.*

Proof. We show both directions as follows.

“ \Rightarrow ” We have that v_S is an admissible model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$. We have to show that S is admissible in \mathcal{F} , i. e.,

- (1) S is conflict-free, and
- (2) S defends all its members.

to (1): Follows directly from the definition of the corresponding model in Equation (5). If S is not conflict-free, then v_S is not well-defined.

to (2): Assume S does not defend itself, i. e., there is some $b \in S^-$ with $b \notin S^+$. Then, the acceptance condition of b is given as $\phi_b = \bigwedge_{a_i \in b^-} \neg a_i$. Since S does not defend against b , we clearly have that $b^- \cap S = \emptyset$. Recall that v_S is an admissible model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$, i. e., we must have $v_S \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v_S)$. Per Equation (5), we have that $v_S(b) = f$. Thus, we must have $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v_S)(b) = f$. $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v_S)(b)$ is defined as

$$\prod \{v'(\phi_b) \mid v' \in [v_S]_2\} = f.$$

It follows that we must have $v_S(a_i) = t$ for all $a_i \in b^-$. However, per Equation (5) we only assign t to some argument a_i if we have that $a_i \in S$. That contradicts the fact that $b^- \cap S = \emptyset$.

Hence, we have that if v_S is an admissible model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ it follows that S is an admissible extension of \mathcal{F} .

“ \Leftarrow ” We have that $S \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F})$. Then, we have to show that v_S is an admissible model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$, i. e., $v_S \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v_S)$. For any argument $a \in \mathcal{A}$, we consider each truth value in $\{t, f, u\}$ individually. Clearly, if $v_S(a) = u$ we have that $v_S(a) \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v_S)(a)$.

Consider now the case $v_S(a) = f$. That directly implies, via Equation (5), that $a \mathcal{R} S$. Since S is admissible, it follows that there exists some $b \in S$ with $b \mathcal{R} a$. From Definition 13 it follows that $\phi_a = \phi' \wedge \neg b$ with ϕ' being some arbitrary conjunctive formula. Per Equation (5), we have that $v_S(b) = t$. It follows that $v'(b) = t$ for all $v' \in [v_S]_2$ and thus $\prod \{v'(\phi_a) \mid v' \in [v_S]_2\} = f$. Hence, we have $v_S(a) \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v_S)(a)$.

Finally, consider the case $v_S(a) = t$. The acceptance condition of a is given as $\phi_a = \bigwedge_{b \in a^-} \neg b$. Per Equation (5), we assign in the model v_S the truth value f to an argument b iff $b \mathcal{R} S$. Thus, $v_S(b) = f$ for all $b \in a^-$. It follows that $\prod \{v'(\phi_a) \mid v' \in [v_S]_2\} = t$. Hence, we have $v_S(a) \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v_S)(a)$.

All in all, it follows that $v_S \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v_S)$ and v_S is an admissible model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$. \square

Theorem 1. *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF and $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is the corresponding ADF. Then $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ is an initial set of \mathcal{F} if and only if v_S is an initial model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$.*

Proof. We show both directions as follows.

“ \Leftarrow ” We have that $S \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$. Then, we have to show that v_S is an initial model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$, i. e.,

- (1) $v_S \neq v_u$, and
- (2) v_S is an admissible model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$, and
- (3) v_S is \leq_i -minimal among the non-empty admissible models of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$.

to (1): Clearly, we have that $S \neq \emptyset$ and thus there exists some $a \in \mathcal{A}$ with $a \in S$. It follows from Equation (5) that $v_S(a) = t$ and thus $v_S \neq v_u$.

to (2): Follows directly from the proof of Proposition 1.

to (3): Assume the contrary. That means, there exists some admissible model v' with $v' \neq v_u$ and $v' \leq_i v_S$. Let S' be the extension of \mathcal{F} that corresponds to v' via Equation (5). Then, w.l.o.g., there exists an argument $a \in \mathcal{A}$ with $v'(a) = u$ and $v_S(a) \neq u$. Consider first the case $v_S(a) = t$. Clearly, that implies $a \in S$ and $a \notin S'$ and together with $v' \leq_i v_S$ it follows that $S' \subsetneq S$. Thus, S cannot be an initial set of \mathcal{F} which contradicts the initial assumption.

Consider now the case $v_S(a) = f$. Per Equation (5), it follows that $a \mathcal{R} S$ in \mathcal{F} . For $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$, it follows that there is some argument $b \in S$ with $v_S(b) = t$ and the acceptance condition $\phi_b = \phi_1 \wedge \neg a$ where ϕ_1 may be some arbitrary formula. Since $a \neq b$, we have that $v'(b) = t$. Clearly, because of $v'(a) = u$ it follows that $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v')(b) \neq t$ and thus $v \not\leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v')$. Hence, v' is not an admissible model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$.

“ \Rightarrow ” We have that v_S is an initial model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$. Dual to the other direction, we have to show that S is an initial set of \mathcal{F} , i. e.,

- (1) $S \neq \emptyset$, and
- (2) $S \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F})$, and
- (3) S is \subseteq -minimal among the non-empty admissible sets of \mathcal{F} .

to (1): Since v_S is an initial model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$, there exists some argument $a \in \mathcal{A}$ with $v_S(a) = \text{t}$. Via Equation (5) it follows directly that $a \in S$ and thus $S \neq \emptyset$.

to (2): Follows directly from the proof of Proposition 1.

to (3): Assume the contrary, i. e., there is some initial set $S' \neq \emptyset$ of \mathcal{F} with $S' \subsetneq S$. We show that for every argument $a \in \mathcal{A}$ we have that $v_{S'}(a) \leq_i v_S(a)$. Consider first the case $v_S(a) = \text{t}$. Assume $v_{S'}(a) = \text{f}$. Per Equation (5) that implies directly that there exists some argument $b \in S'$ (and thus also $b \in S$) with $a\mathcal{R}b$. That means S is not conflict-free, which is not possible. It follows that $v_{S'}$ assigns either t or u to a .

Consider now the case $v_S(a) = \text{f}$. Assume $v_{S'}(a) = \text{t}$. That would mean $S' \not\subseteq S$. It follows that $v_{S'}$ assigns either f or u to a .

Finally, consider the case $v_S(a) = \text{u}$. Like before, if $v_{S'}(a) = \text{t}$ we have that $S' \not\subseteq S$. Assume $v_{S'}(a) = \text{f}$. That implies $a\mathcal{R}S'$. However, because of $S' \subset S$ it follows $a\mathcal{R}S$ and thus $v_S(a) = \text{f}$.

Therefore, it follows that $v_{S'}(a) \leq_i v_S(a)$ for all arguments $a \in \mathcal{A}$. From the “ \Rightarrow ”-direction it follows that $v_{S'}$ is admissible in $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ and because of $v_{S'} \leq_i v_S$ we arrive at a contradiction. \square

4 Serialisability in ADFs

Lemma 1. *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and v_1, v_2 be admissible models of \mathcal{D} . If v_1 and v_2 are not in conflict with each other, then $v_1 \sqcup v_2$ is an admissible model of \mathcal{D} .*

Proof. Given $v_1 \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D})$ and $v_2 \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1})$, we consider the model $v = v_1 \sqcup v_2$. Recall that v_1 and v_2 are non-conflicting. We only have to show that $v \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$. Assume the contrary. Then there must be some argument $a \in \mathcal{A}$ such that $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)(a) = \text{u}$ and $v(a) \neq \text{u}$. We distinguish between two cases:

$v_1(a) \neq \text{u}$ We distinguish further between:

$v_1(a) = \text{t}$ We know that $v_1 \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D})$ and thus $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v_1)(a) = \text{t}$. That means all two-valued completions of v_1 assign t to a . For any model v' with $v_1 \leq_i v'$ we know that $[v'] \leq [v_1]$. Clearly, it follows that any model v' must then also assign t to a . Recall that $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}$ is defined as the consensus over the set of completions of v . Since we have $v_1 \leq_i v$, it follows that $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)(a) = \text{t}$.

$v_1(a) = \text{f}$ This follows analogously to the previous case.

It follows that for all arguments that are assigned t or f in v_1 , that they are also assigned the same value in $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$.
 $v_2(a) \neq \text{u}$ The claim follows analogously to the previous case.

It follows that $v \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$ and thus $v = v_1 \sqcup v_2$ is admissible in \mathcal{D} . \square

Theorem 2. *A serialisation sequence $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ induces an admissible model $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ and for every admissible model there is at least one such sequence.*

Proof. We show both directions as follows.

“ \Rightarrow ” Let $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ be a serialisation sequence of the ADF $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$. We show that it follows that $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D})$ by induction over the length of the serialisation sequence $n = |(v_1, \dots, v_n)|$.

($n = 0$) We have that $\mathcal{Y} = ()$ and it follows directly that $v_{\text{u}} \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D})$.

($n \rightarrow n + 1$) Per assumption we have that $\mathcal{Y}' = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ is a serialisation sequence and $v' = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ is an admissible model of \mathcal{D} . Now, per Definition 19 we know that $v_{n+1} \in \text{is}(\mathcal{D}^{v'})$ and thus also $v_{n+1} \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D}^{v'})$. It follows directly from Corollary 2 that $v = v' \sqcup v_{n+1}$ is an admissible model of \mathcal{D} .

“ \Leftarrow ” Let v be an admissible model of the ADF $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$. We show that there exists a serialisation sequence $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ by induction over the number of arguments assigned t or f in v , i. e., $m = |\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v(a) \neq \text{u}\}|$.

($m = 0$) We have that $v = v_{\text{u}}$ and trivially the corresponding serialisation sequence $\mathcal{Y} = ()$.

($m \rightarrow m + 1$) Consider the model $v \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D})$ with $|\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v(a) \neq \text{u}\}| = m + 1$. Now, if $v \in \text{is}(\mathcal{D})$ we have the serialisation sequence (v) of \mathcal{D} . Otherwise, it follows from Definition 14 that there exists some $v_0 \leq_i v$ with $v_0 \in \text{is}(\mathcal{D})$. Consider the model $v' = v \setminus v_0$ defined as follows:

$$v'(a) = \begin{cases} v(a) & \text{if } v_0(a) = \text{u} \\ \text{undefined} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Meaning, v' assigns the same values as v if v_0 assigns u and otherwise v' assigns nothing. In other words, v' is the part of v that is concerned only with the reduct \mathcal{D}^{v_0} . We now have to show that $v' \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D}^{v_0})$. We distinguish between three cases:
 $v'(a) = \text{u}$ Clearly, we always have $v(a)' \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}^{v_0}}(v')(a)$.

$v'(a) = \text{t}$ Per definition, if v' assigns t (or f) to some argument, then v also assigns t (respectively f). Consider the arguments where v assigns t or f and v' is undefined. Those are exactly the arguments where v_0 assigns t or f . Now, per Definition 17 of the reduct wrt v_0 , the occurrences of the arguments in all acceptance conditions in \mathcal{D}^{v_0} are replaced with \top and \perp respectively. That is exactly the same as taking the acceptance conditions of \mathcal{D} and assigning t or f to

the respective arguments in every completion of v' for which v' is undefined. It is easy to see that we then have $v'(a) =_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}^{v_0}} = t$.

$v'(a) = f$ Analogous to the previous case.

It follows that $v' \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D}^{v_0})$. From the fact that $v_0 \neq v_u$ it follows directly that $|\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v(a) \neq u\}| \leq m$. Thus, we know that there exists a serialisation sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) with $v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n = v'$. It follows that $\mathcal{Y} = (v_0, v_1, \dots, v_n)$ is a serialisation sequence of \mathcal{D} with $v_0 \sqcup v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n = v$. \square

5 Characterising Serialisable Semantics in ADFs

Theorem 3. *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \{t, f, u\}$ is an interpretation. We have that $v \in \text{pr}(\mathcal{D})$ if and only if there is a serialisation sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) of \mathcal{D} with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ and it holds that $\text{is}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}) = \emptyset$.*

Proof. We prove both directions as follows:

“ \Rightarrow ” Let $v \in \text{pr}(\mathcal{D})$ be a preferred model of \mathcal{D} . Then, by definition v is also admissible and thus there exists some serialisation sequence $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$. Now assume that $\text{is}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}) \neq \emptyset$. That means, there exists some initial model v' . Per Corollary 2 it follows directly that $v \sqcup v'$ is an admissible model of \mathcal{D} which contradicts the assumption that v is a preferred model of \mathcal{D} .

“ \Leftarrow ” Let $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ be a serialisation sequence such that $\text{is}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}) = \emptyset$. We know that $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ is an admissible model of \mathcal{D} . Assume that v is not preferred, i.e., there exists some admissible model v' with $v \leq_i v'$. Per Corollary 2 it follows directly that there is some admissible model v'' in \mathcal{D}^v with $v' = v \sqcup v''$. It follows that either $v'' \in \text{is}(\mathcal{D}^v)$ or there exists some other $v_{n+1} \in \text{is}(\mathcal{D}^v)$ with $v_{n+1} <_i v''$. That contradicts the assumption that $\text{is}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}) = \emptyset$. \square

Theorem 4. *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \{t, f, u\}$ is an interpretation. We have that $v \in \text{co}(\mathcal{D})$ if and only if there is a serialisation sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) of \mathcal{D} with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ and $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}) = \emptyset$.*

Proof. We show both directions as follows.

“ \Rightarrow ” Let $v \in \text{co}(\mathcal{D})$. Then there is some serialisation sequence $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$. Assume that $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{D}^v) \neq \emptyset$, i.e., there exists some unattacked initial model v' in \mathcal{D}^v . Then, per Definition 16 and Corollary 1 it follows that v' only assigns t or f to exactly one argument $a \in \mathcal{A}$ and that the acceptance condition ϕ'_a for that argument in the ADF \mathcal{D}^v is a tautology or unsatisfiable, respectively. Furthermore, since the argument a is in the reduct \mathcal{D}^v , we know that $v(a) = u$. Recall that per Definition 17 in the acceptance condition of the reduct all occurrences of the arguments assigned t or f by v are replaced by their truth value. Now, if we consider the acceptance condition ϕ_a of a in \mathcal{D} , this is exactly what is done when applying the characteristic operator $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}$ on the model v . That means we obtain

$\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)(a) = t$ if ϕ'_a is a tautology (respectively f if ϕ'_a is unsatisfiable). That means we have $v <_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$ and thus a contradiction to the assumption that v is complete in \mathcal{D} .

“ \Leftarrow ” Let $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ be a serialisation sequence such that $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}) = \emptyset$. From Theorem 2 it follows that $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ is an admissible model of \mathcal{D} . It remains to show that v is complete, i.e., that we have $v = \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$. Assume the contrary, i.e., there is some argument $a \in \mathcal{A}$ such that $v(a) = u$ and $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)(a) \neq u$. Assume, without loss of generality, that $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)(a) = t$. That means, in every completion of v the argument a is assigned t, regardless of the assignment of arguments assigned u by v . In other words, when fixing all arguments assigned t or f by v to their respective truth value, the acceptance condition ϕ_a is tautological. It is easy to see that this is exactly the acceptance condition ϕ'_a of the argument a in the reduct \mathcal{D}^v . It follows that v' with

$$v'(b) = \begin{cases} t & \text{if } b=a \\ u & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

is an unattacked initial model of \mathcal{D}^v and we arrive at a contradiction. \square

Theorem 5. *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \{t, f, u\}$ is an interpretation. We have that $v \in \text{gr}(\mathcal{D})$ if and only if there is a serialisation sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) of \mathcal{D} with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ and for all $v_i, i = 1, \dots, n$, it holds that $v_i \in \text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_{i-1}})$ and $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}) = \emptyset$.*

Proof. We show both directions as follows.

“ \Rightarrow ” Let $v \in \text{gr}(\mathcal{D})$ be the unique grounded model of \mathcal{D} . Recall from Definition 10 that the grounded model is computed iteratively via the function $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}$ starting with $v_1 = v_u$. The grounded model is then the model v_k such that $v_k = v_{k-1}$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}$ is the smallest number satisfying this condition.

We construct a corresponding serialisation \mathcal{Y} sequence as follows. We start with $\mathcal{Y} = ()$. Consider first $v_2 = \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v_u)$. We distinguish between three cases:

$$(1.1) \quad |\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v_2(a) \neq u\}| = 1$$

Let a be the argument assigned t or f by v_2 . Since $v_1 = v_u$ it follows directly that $\phi_a \in \text{TAUT}_{\mathcal{A}}$ or $\phi_a \in \text{UNSAT}_{\mathcal{A}}$. Clearly v'_1 with

$$v'_1(b) = \begin{cases} v_2(b) & \text{if } b = a, \\ u & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

is then an unattacked initial model of \mathcal{D} . The corresponding serialisation sequence is updated to $\mathcal{Y} = (v'_1)$.

$$(1.2) \quad |\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v_2(a) \neq u\}| > 1$$

We denote $\mathcal{A}' = \{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v_2(a) \neq u\}$. Like in (1.1) we know that $\phi_a \in \text{TAUT}_{\mathcal{A}}$ or $\phi_a \in \text{UNSAT}_{\mathcal{A}}$ for all $a \in \mathcal{A}'$. Clearly, if ϕ_a is a tautology (or unsatisfiable) then this will also be the case after substituting any subset of its atoms with arbitrary truth values t or f, i.e., any ϕ'_a of any possible reduct of

\mathcal{D} will still be a tautology (respectively unsatisfiable). Let $<$ be some arbitrary order over the arguments \mathcal{A}' and (a_1, \dots, a_m) is then an ordered list of the arguments in \mathcal{A}' . Then $\mathcal{Y}' = (v'_1, \dots, v'_m)$ is a serialisation sequence with v'_i for $1 \leq i \leq m$ defined as

$$v'_i(b) = \begin{cases} v_2(a) & \text{if } b = a_i, \\ u & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The corresponding serialisation sequence is updated to $\mathcal{Y} = \mathcal{Y}'$.

$$(1.3) \quad |\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v_2(a) \neq u\}| = 0$$

We have that $v_2 = v_1 = v_u$ and thus v_2 is the grounded model of \mathcal{D} with the corresponding serialisation sequence $\mathcal{Y} = ()$.

Consider now $v_i = \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v_{i-1})$ for any $1 < i \leq n$. We distinguish between the same three cases.

$$(2.1) \quad |\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v_i(a) \neq u\}| = 1 \text{ Like in the case (1.1), the model } v_j \text{ that only assigns t (or f) to one argument } a \text{ is added to the sequence.}$$

$$(2.2) \quad |\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v_i(a) \neq u\}| > 1 \text{ Again, like in case (1.2) we add one model for each argument assigned t or f to the sequence.}$$

$$(2.3) \quad |\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v_i(a) \neq u\}| = 0 \text{ The fixpoint of } \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}} \text{ is reached and we have that } v_{i-1} \text{ is the grounded model of } \mathcal{D} \text{ and } \mathcal{Y} \text{ is a grounded serialisation sequence corresponding to } v_{i_1}.$$

Thus, we have that there is at least one grounded serialisation sequence that corresponds to the grounded model of \mathcal{D} .

“ \Leftarrow ” Let $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ be a serialisation sequence such that $v_i \in \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_{i-1}})$ for every i with $1 \leq i \leq n$ and $\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}) = \emptyset$. Denote with v_{gr} the unique grounded model of \mathcal{D} and with $\hat{v}_i = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_i$ the partial model at step i for $1 \leq i \leq n$.

We first show that $\hat{v}_i \leq_i v_{\text{gr}}$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$ by induction over i .

($i = 1$) We have that $\hat{v}_1 = v_1$ and by definition $\hat{v}_1 \in \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{D})$. Let a be the unique argument assigned either t or f by v_1 . Per Definition 16 it follows that $\phi_a \in \text{TAUT}_{\mathcal{A}}$ or $\phi_a \in \text{UNSAT}_{\mathcal{A}}$. Clearly, that implies directly that $v_{\text{gr}}(a) = \text{t}$ (or f respectively) and therefore $\hat{v}_1 \leq_1 v_{\text{gr}}$.

($i > 1$) By assumption, we have that $\hat{v}_i = v' \sqcup \hat{v}_{i-1}$ with $v' \in \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_{i-1}})$. Again, let a be the unique argument assigned t or f by v' . Assume w.l.o.g. that $v'(a) = \text{t}$. It follows that $\phi'_a \in \text{TAUT}_{\mathcal{A}}$ with ϕ'_a being the acceptance condition of a in the reduct $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_{i-1}}$. Now, as already shown in the proof of Lemma 1, if an acceptance condition ϕ'_a is true wrt. a model v' in the reduct $ADF^{\hat{v}_{i-1}}$ then the acceptance condition ϕ_a of \mathcal{D} is true for the model $\hat{v}_{i-1} \sqcup v'$. Thus, since by assumption we have that $\hat{v}_{i-1} \leq_i v_{\text{gr}}$, it follows that $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v_{\text{gr}}) = \text{t}$ and therefore $v_{\text{gr}}(a) = \text{t}$. Hence, it follows that $\hat{v}_i \leq_i v_{\text{gr}}$.

From Theorem 4 it follows directly that $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ is a complete model of \mathcal{D} , i. e., $v \leq_i v_{\text{gr}}$.

Thus, we have $v = v_{\text{gr}}$. \square

Theorem 6. Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \{\text{t}, \text{f}, \text{u}\}$ is an interpretation. We have that $v \in \text{val}_2(\mathcal{D})$ if and only if there is a serialisation sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) of \mathcal{D} with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ and it holds that $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n} = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$.

Proof. We show both directions as follows.

“ \Rightarrow ” Let $v \in \text{val}_2(\mathcal{D})$ be a two-valued model of \mathcal{D} . It follows directly from definition 9 of the characteristic operator that $v = \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$ and thus $v \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D})$. It follows that there exists a serialisation sequence $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$. Since v is a two-valued model we have that $|\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v(a) = \text{u}\}| = 0$ and it follows directly that the v -reduct of \mathcal{D} is $\mathcal{D}^v = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$.

“ \Leftarrow ” Let $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ be a serialisation sequence such that $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n} = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$. Per definition $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ is an admissible model of \mathcal{D} . It remains to show that v does not assign u to any argument $a \in \mathcal{A}$. Clearly, if there were such arguments, then we can construct the v -reduct $\mathcal{D}^v = (\mathcal{A}', \mathcal{C}')$ with

$$\mathcal{A}' = \mathcal{A} \setminus \{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v(a) \neq \text{u}\}$$

and we would have $|\mathcal{A}'| \neq 0$ which contradicts the assumption. \square

6 Computational Complexity

First, we recall the complexity of deciding whether $v \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$ which has been shown in [Strass and Wallner, 2015] to be in coNP via approximation fixpoint theory.

Lemma 2. Given an ADF $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ and a model v of \mathcal{D} , deciding whether $v \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$ is in coNP.

Proof. This follows directly from Theorem 3.18 of [Strass and Wallner, 2015]. Technically, in [Strass and Wallner, 2015] interpretations are represented as pairs (X, Y) with $X \subseteq Y \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. However, they can clearly be interchanged by mappings $v : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \{\text{t}, \text{f}, \text{u}\}$ into the set of truth values. A pair (X, Y) represents a three-valued interpretation v defined as follows

$$v(a) = \begin{cases} \text{t} & \text{if } a \in X \\ \text{f} & \text{if } a \in \mathcal{A} \setminus Y \\ \text{u} & \text{if } a \in Y \setminus X \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

In particular, they consider the problem of verifying for a pair (X, Y) whether $(X, Y) \leq_i \mathcal{O}(X, Y)$, where \mathcal{O} is an approximating operator on the consistent complete partially ordered set (\mathcal{A}^c, \leq_i) and \mathcal{A}^c is the set of all consistent pairs of sets of arguments. In other words, \mathcal{O} approximates the characteristic operator $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}$. They show that this problem amounts to verifying whether for the lower bound $\mathcal{O}'(X, Y)$ we have that $X \subseteq \mathcal{O}'(X, Y)$ and for the upper bound $\mathcal{O}''(X, Y)$ whether $\mathcal{O}''(X, Y) \subseteq Y$. Both of these checks are in coNP as per Lemma 3.17 of [Strass and Wallner, 2015].

It follows that deciding whether $v \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$ is in coNP. \square

To facilitate checking the \leq_i -minimality of an admissible model, we generalise Lemma 1 of [Thimm, 2022] for deciding whether for a given set S there exists an admissible subset from AFs to ADFs as follows. Notably, while this can be done in polynomial time (just like verifying admissibility) in the case of AFs, for ADFs checking the minimality of an admissible model proves to be computationally harder.

Lemma 3. *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \{t, f, u\}$ is an interpretation. The problem of deciding whether there exists a model $v' \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D})$ with $v' \leq_i v$ and $v'(a) \neq u$ is in $P_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$.*

Proof. To decide the above problem, consider the following polynomial time algorithm with access to an NP oracle. Recall, that a NP oracle is equivalent to a coNP oracle. First, we verify whether v is an admissible model of \mathcal{D} , which can be done in coNP (see Lemma 2). If v is not admissible we consider the following construction: Let $v_0 = v$. We define v_i for $i \in \mathbb{N}$ as follows

$$v_i(a) = \begin{cases} v_{i-1}(a) & \text{if } v_{i-1}(a) \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v_{i-1})(a) \\ u & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Now, clearly we have $v_i <_i v_{i-1}$ for every i , otherwise v_{i-1} would have been admissible. For every v_i we then verify the following:

- (1) If $v_i(a) = u$, we have that a can never be assigned t or f in any $v' \leq_i v_i$ and thus it follows that no such model v' exists and we return *false*.
- (2) Otherwise, we have $v_i(a) \neq u$ and we verify whether v_i is admissible. If yes, we return *true*, otherwise we continue with $i \rightarrow i + 1$.

The set of arguments assigned t or f by v has the size $n = |\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v(a) \neq u\}|$ and we have $v_i <_i v_{i-1}$ for every i . Thus, we will make at most n steps, each making an independent check in coNP. It follows that the algorithm runs in $P_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$. \square

Based on Lemmas 2 and 3 it follows that VER_{is} is in $P_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ and it can be shown to be coNP-hard. We conjecture that VER_{is} is $P_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ -hard, but a formal proof is missing at the moment. We show each statement of Theorem 7 individually split into Propositions 2 to 5.

Proposition 2. *VER_{is} is in $P_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ and coNP-hard.*

Proof. Membership follows from Lemmas 2 and 3. In particular, we first verify in coNP whether v is an admissible model of \mathcal{D} . Then, for every pair of arguments $a_1, a_2 \in \{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v(a) \neq u\}$ with $a_1 \neq a_2$ we verify whether for the model v' with

$$v'(a) = \begin{cases} u & \text{if } a = a_2 \\ v(a) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

there exists a model v'' with $v'' \leq_i v'$ and $v''(a) \neq u$. If one such pair exists, then v is not an initial model of \mathcal{D} . If no such model exists, then v is an initial model of \mathcal{D} . This amounts to

a polynomial number of independent checks, each in coNP, cf. Lemma 3, and thus the algorithm runs in $P_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$.

For coNP-hardness we utilise the reduction RED_1 from [Strass and Wallner, 2015]. Let ψ be a propositional formula over the vocabulary P , then we define the ADF $\text{RED}_1 = (P \cup \{z\}, \mathcal{C})$ where $z \notin P$ is a variable and the acceptance conditions defined as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_p &= \neg p & \text{for } p \in P, \\ \phi_z &= \psi. \end{aligned}$$

Then, we have that ψ is unsatisfiable if and only if v with

$$v(a) = \begin{cases} f & \text{if } a = z \\ u & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

is an initial model of RED_1 . We show both directions as follows.

“ \Rightarrow ” We have that ψ is unsatisfiable. Per Lemma 3.9 of [Strass and Wallner, 2015] it follows that for any argument $a \in \mathcal{A}$ if $\phi_a = \neg a$, then we have $v(a) = u$ for any admissible model v . Thus, we know that $v(p) = u$ for any $p \in P$ for any admissible model v . Furthermore, per definition z does not occur in $\phi_z = \psi$ and since ψ is unsatisfiable it follows directly that $v(z) = f$ for any model of RED_1 . Clearly, that means $v \neq v_u$. The minimality of v follows immediately since the only model v' with $v' \leq_i v$ is the model v_u .

“ \Leftarrow ” We have that v with

$$v(a) = \begin{cases} f & \text{if } a = z \\ u & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

is an initial model of RED_1 . From $v \leq_i \Gamma_{\text{RED}_1}(v)$ and the fact that v assigns u to every $p \in P$ it follows directly that $\Gamma_{\text{RED}_1}(v)(z) = f$ and thus that every possible truth value assignment to the atoms of ψ yields that ψ is false and thus unsatisfiable.

It follows that VER_{is} is coNP-hard. \square

The problem $\text{EXISTS}_{\text{is}}$ is equivalent to $\text{EXISTS}_{\text{ad}}^{-\emptyset}$ and thus the following result follows directly.

Proposition 3. *$\text{EXISTS}_{\text{is}}$ and $\text{EXISTS}_{\text{is}}^{-\emptyset}$ are Σ_2^P -complete.*

Proof. Both problems are clearly equivalent, since v_u can explicitly not be an initial model of any ADF. Furthermore, the problem is equivalent to the problem of deciding whether there exists a non-trivial admissible model for \mathcal{D} , i.e., the problem $\text{EXISTS}_{\text{ad}}^{-\emptyset}$. Thus, the result follows directly from the proof of Theorem 4.15 in [Strass and Wallner, 2015]. \square

Before we turn to the complexity of credulous and skeptical reasoning wrt. initial models in ADFs, we consider again the complexity class $P_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$. As the following lemma shows, this class brings no more expressivity than NP when used as an oracle for a polynomial-time complexity class.

Lemma 4. *$NP_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}} = \Sigma_2^P$ and $\text{coNP}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}} = \Pi_2^P$.*

Proof. We only show $\text{NP}^{\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}} = \Sigma_2^P$, the other statement follows analogically.

We show $\text{NP}^{\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}} \supseteq \Sigma_2^P$ and $\text{NP}^{\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}} \subseteq \Sigma_2^P$. Remember that $\Sigma_2^P = \text{NP}^{\text{NP}}$.

- $\text{NP}^{\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}} \supseteq \text{NP}^{\text{NP}}$:

Note that $\text{NP} \subseteq \text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ since any problem in NP can be solved by a single call to an NP oracle (without any need for parallelism). It follows that any problem in NP^{NP} can be solved by using $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ oracle calls instead of NP oracle calls.

- $\text{NP}^{\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}} \subseteq \text{NP}^{\text{NP}}$:

We show the stronger statement $\text{NP}^{\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}} \subseteq \text{NP}^{\text{NP}}$ (which implies the above statement due to $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}} \subseteq \text{P}^{\text{NP}}$).

Let $Q \in \text{NP}^{\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}}$ be a problem and A_Q be an $\text{NP}^{\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}}$ -algorithm for Q . Let I be an instance for Q , then executing A_Q on I , written as $A_Q(I)$, gives the following algorithm trace:

$$A_Q(I) = \text{np}_1 \circ O_1^{\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}} \circ \text{np}_2 \circ O_2^{\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}} \circ \dots \circ \text{np}_{k-1} \circ O_{k-1}^{\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}} \circ \text{np}_k \quad (8)$$

with $k \in O(|I|^K)$ for some $K \in \mathbb{N}$, each np_i ($i = 1, \dots, k$) is a non-deterministic algorithm running in polynomial time (wrt. $|I|$), and each $O_i^{\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}}$ ($i = 1, \dots, k-1$) is a one-step call to a $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ -oracle (and \circ denotes concatenation of the sub-algorithms). Without loss of generality and to ease notation, let us assume that each $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ -oracle call in the above trace can be realised by an P^{NP} -algorithm B that has the following algorithm trace:

$$B = \text{p}_1 \circ O_1^{\text{NP}} \circ \dots \circ \text{p}_{k'-1} \circ O_{k'-1}^{\text{NP}} \circ \text{p}_{k'}$$

with $k' \in O(|I|^{K'})$ for some $K' \in \mathbb{N}$, each p_i ($i = 1, \dots, k'$) is a deterministic algorithm running in polynomial time (wrt. $|I|$), and each O_i^{NP} ($i = 1, \dots, k'-1$) is a one-step call to a NP -oracle. Substituting each oracle call in (8) with B gives us a new algorithm A'_Q :

$$A'_Q(I) = \text{np}_1 \circ \left[\text{p}_1 \circ O_1^{\text{NP}} \circ \dots \circ \text{p}_{k'-1} \circ O_{k'-1}^{\text{NP}} \circ \text{p}_{k'} \right] \\ \circ \dots \circ \\ \text{np}_{k-1} \circ \left[\text{p}_1 \circ O_1^{\text{NP}} \circ \dots \circ \text{p}_{k'-1} \circ O_{k'-1}^{\text{NP}} \circ \text{p}_{k'} \right] \\ \circ \text{np}_k$$

Note that $A'_Q(I)$ also solves Q (we only substituted oracle calls with concrete algorithms for the corresponding problems). Observe that each deterministic algorithm running in polynomial time can also be understood as a non-deterministic algorithm running in polynomial time and concatenating a non-deterministic algorithm running in polynomial time with a deterministic algorithm running in polynomial time is just a non-deterministic algorithm running in polynomial time. So we can write

“ np ” for algorithms of type “ p ” and “ np ” for “ $\text{np} \circ \text{p}$ ”. Let $k'' = (k-1) * (k'-1)$, then the algorithm trace of $A'_Q(I)$ can be written as

$$A'_Q(I) = \text{np}_1 \circ O_1^{\text{NP}} \circ \dots \circ \text{np}_{k''-1} \circ O_{k''-1}^{\text{NP}} \circ \text{np}_{k''}$$

Note that $k'' \in O(|I|^{K''})$ for some $K'' \in \mathbb{N}$, so A'_Q is a NP^{NP} -algorithm, showing $Q \in \text{NP}^{\text{NP}}$ and therefore $\text{NP}^{\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}} \subseteq \text{NP}^{\text{NP}}$. \square

It follows then that CRED_{IS} and SKEPT_{IS} are on the second level of the polynomial hierarchy, just like the corresponding problems for ad in ADFs.

Proposition 4. CRED_{IS} is Σ_2^P -complete.

Proof. For membership, consider the following algorithm. Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be the input ADF and $a \in \mathcal{A}$. We non-deterministically guess a model v with $v(a) \neq u$ and verify whether v is initial in $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$. Together with Lemma 4 it follows then directly that CRED_{IS} is in Σ_2^P .

For Σ_2^P -hardness, we adapt the reduction RED_2 of [Strass and Wallner, 2015] from the problem of deciding whether a quantified boolean formula $\exists P \forall Q : \psi$ is true.

Let P and Q be disjoint sets of variables and ψ is a formula over $P \cup Q$. Let x, y and z be fresh variables and we define the set $-P = \{-p \mid p \in P\}$.

Then we define the reduction as the ADF $\mathcal{D}_{\psi} = (\mathcal{A}_{\psi}, \mathcal{C}_{\psi})$ with

$$\mathcal{A}_{\psi} = P \cup -P \cup Q \cup \{x, y, z\}$$

and the acceptance conditions $\phi \in \mathcal{C}_{\psi}$ are defined as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_p &= \neg x \wedge \neg z \wedge \neg p && \text{for } p \in P \\ \phi_{-p} &= \neg x \wedge \neg z \wedge \neg p && \text{for } -p \in -P \\ \phi_q &= \neg z \wedge \neg q && \text{for } q \in Q \\ \phi_x &= \neg x \wedge \neg \psi \\ \phi_y &= \neg x \\ \phi_z &= \neg y \end{aligned}$$

The reduction is polynomial in the size of $P \cup Q$. First, we recall two properties of the techniques used in the above encoding, shown in Lemmas 3.9 and 3.11 of [Strass and Wallner, 2015]. All arguments $q \in Q$ will be assigned u in every admissible model of \mathcal{D}_{ψ} . Secondly, if x is assigned u , then all arguments $p \in P$ and $-p \in -P$ are also assigned u . Similarly, it follows that if z is assigned u then all $p \in P, -p \in -P$ and $q \in Q$ are also assigned u .

Figure 1 shows an example of the construction for $\psi = (p_1 \wedge \neg p_2) \vee q_1$. The intuition behind the reduction is the following: If $\exists P \forall Q : \psi$ is false, then v_u is the only admissible model of \mathcal{D}_{ψ} and thus we have no initial model and trivially no argument can be credulously accepted. On the other hand, if $\exists P \forall Q : \psi$ is true, then there exists at least one subset $P' \subseteq P$ that makes ψ true for all $q \in Q$ and we have a corresponding admissible model where y and all $p \in P'$ are assigned t , all $q \in Q$ are assigned u and the rest of the arguments are assigned f . We can then show that y is assigned

Figure 1: The ADF \mathcal{D}_ψ for $\psi = (p_1 \wedge \neg p_2) \vee q_1$ from the proof of Proposition 4.

t in every such admissible model and thus also in the initial models of \mathcal{D}_ψ .

We will now show that this claim holds, i. e., if and only if $\exists P\forall Q : \psi$ is true, then y is credulously accepted wrt. initial models, i. e., there exists a model $v \in \text{is}(\mathcal{D}_\psi)$ with $v(y) = \text{t}$.

“ \Rightarrow ” Assume the QBF $\exists P\forall Q : \psi$ is true. Then there exists some $P' \subseteq P$ such that for all $Q' \subseteq Q$ we have that $P' \cup Q' \models \phi$. We denote $M = P' \cup \{-p \mid p \in P \setminus P'\}$. Consider the model v with

$$v(a) = \begin{cases} \text{t} & \text{if } a \in \{y\} \cup M, \\ \text{f} & \text{if } a \in \{x, z\} \text{ or } a \notin M, \\ \text{u} & \text{if } a \in Q. \end{cases}$$

We have to show that $v \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_\psi}(v)$. Clearly, for all $q \in Q$ this holds trivially. Now, for every $p \in P'$ it follows directly that $v'(\phi_p) = \text{t}$ for every $v' \in [v]_2$, and thus $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_\psi}(v)(p) = v(p) = \text{t}$. Analogously, the same follows for every $-p$ with $p \in P \setminus P'$. For every $p \in P \setminus P'$ it is easy to see that we have $v'(\phi_p) = \text{f}$ for every $v' \in [v]_2$ and thus $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_\psi}(v)(p) = v(p) = \text{f}$. Again, the same follows analogously for every $-p$ with $p \in P'$. For y we have that $\phi_y = \neg x$, so clearly we have $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_\psi}(\phi_y) = \text{t}$ since $v'(z) = \text{f}$ for every $v' \in [v]_2$. Analogously it follows for z that $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_\psi}(z) = \text{f}$. Finally, for x we need to show that $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_\psi}(x) = \text{f}$. By assumption we know that for any X with $M \subseteq X \subseteq M \cup Q$ we have that $X \models \psi$. Therefore, we have that $X \not\models \phi_x$. It follows that ϕ_x is unsatisfiable and thus $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_\psi}(x) = \text{f}$.

We know now that v is an admissible model of \mathcal{D}_ψ and it remains to show that we have $v'(y) = \text{t}$ for any admissible model v' with $v' <_i v$ and $v' \neq v_u$. Assume the contrary, i. e., there is an admissible model v' with $v'(y) = \text{u}$ and $v' \leq_i v$. Then it follows directly from the acceptance condition ϕ_z of z that $v'(z) = \text{u}$ and from the acceptance condition ϕ_y of y that we must have $v'(x) = \text{u}$. Recall that for every $q \in Q$ we always assign u in every admissible model. Furthermore, recall that if x is assigned u then every $p \in P$ and every $-p \in -P$ must also be assigned u in every admissible model. Clearly,

that directly implies that $v' = v_u$. Therefore, every non-trivial admissible model of \mathcal{D}_ψ must at least assign f to x and t to y and it follows that y is credulously accepted wrt. initial model if $\exists P\forall Q : \psi$ is true.

“ \Leftarrow ” Assume that y is credulously accepted wrt. initial models in \mathcal{D}_ψ . That means there is some initial model v with $v(y) = \text{t}$. We can infer that we must have $v(x) = \text{f}$ due to the acceptance condition $\phi_y = \neg x$. Consider the acceptance condition $\phi_x = \neg x \wedge \neg\psi$. Per definition we have that $v(\neg x) = \text{f}$ or $v(\neg\psi) = \text{f}$. Clearly $v(\neg x) = \text{f}$ is impossible since $v(x) = \text{f}$. It follows that $v(\neg\psi) = \text{f}$ and thus $v(\psi) = \text{t}$. Therefore, we have that $\exists P\forall Q : \psi$ is true.

It follows that CRED_{is} is Σ_2^P -hard. \square

Proposition 5. SKEPT_{is} is Π_2^P -complete.

Proof. For membership, consider the complement problem, i. e., deciding whether there exists an initial model $v : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \{\text{t}, \text{f}, \text{u}\}$ with $v(a) = \text{u}$. For that, we non-deterministically guess a model v with $v(a) = \text{u}$ and verify in $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ that v is initial. Meaning, the algorithm runs in $\text{NP}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ and thus the problem SKEPT_{is} is in $\text{coNP}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$. It follows from Lemma 4 that this class is equivalent to Π_2^P .

For Π_2^P -hardness, we show that the complement problem, i. e. deciding whether there exists an initial model $v : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \{\text{t}, \text{f}, \text{u}\}$ with $v(a) = \text{u}$, is Σ_2^P -hard. For that, consider the reduction \mathcal{D}_ψ from the proof of Proposition 4. In particular, we will show that if and only if $\exists P\forall Q : \psi$ is true, then x is not skeptically accepted, i. e., there exists an initial model v with $v(x) = \text{u}$ or $v(x) = \text{f}$.

“ \Rightarrow ” We have that $\exists P\forall Q : \psi$ is true. As shown before, then in all initial models the argument x will be assigned f and there exists at least one such model corresponding to an assignment of variables in P that make ψ true. Thus, z is not skeptically accepted.

“ \Leftarrow ” Assume x is not skeptically accepted, i. e., there is some initial model v in which z is assigned u or f . As discussed in the proof of Proposition 4, from

Lemma 3.11 of [Strass and Wallner, 2015] it follows from $v(x) = u$ that all arguments $p \in P$ and $q \in Q$ are assigned u as well. Furthermore, it follows from the acceptance conditions of every $-p \in -P$ that $v(-p) = u$ and thus we have $v = v_u$ which cannot be an initial model, meaning there can be no initial model of \mathcal{D}_ψ that assigns u to x . Therefore, the second case must apply, i. e., we have an initial model v with $v(x) = f$. From $v(x) = f$ it follows then directly, as shown in the proof of Proposition 4, that $\exists P \forall Q : \psi$ is true.

Thus, the complement problem of SKEPT_{IS} is Σ_2^P -hard and the problem SKEPT_{IS} is then Π_2^P -hard. \square

References

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